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Journal of Business and Economic Analysis, Vol. 7, No. 1 (2024) 61-90

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**PERCEPTIONS AND VIABILITY OF ISLAMIC WEALTH MANAGEMENT
AMONG STAFF AT THE ISLAMIC UNIVERSITY IN
UGANDA, KAMPALA CAMPUS, KIBULI KAMPALA (IUIU-KC)**

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Received 31 July 2024

Revised 6 November 2024

Accepted 11 November 2024

Published 30 April 2024

This study investigates the role of attitudes, behavioral beliefs, and normative beliefs in shaping the intention to adopt Islamic Wealth Management (IWM) among staff at the Islamic

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University in Uganda, Kampala Campus (IUIU-KC). Given the varied perceptions surrounding IWM understanding these influencing factors is crucial for its viability among stakeholders. Employing a qualitative exploratory approach, data were collected through interviews with purposively selected academicians from the Faculty of Management Studies. Thematic analysis revealed that positive attitudes, supportive behavioral beliefs, and favorable normative beliefs significantly encourage IWM adoption. The findings imply that fostering these positive perceptions can enhance IWM integration within educational and financial institutions. By understanding these key drivers, policymakers, educators, and financial institutions can develop targeted strategies to promote IWM adoption. This approach not only aids stakeholder engagement and curriculum refinement in higher education institutions (HEIs) but also supports informed policy-making, advancing the broader acceptance and integration of IWM in Uganda and similar contexts. Further still IWM may be an option towards achieving the 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals if implemented.

Keywords: Islamic Wealth Management, Attitude, Behavior, Norms, IUIU-KC

1. Introduction

Wealth, as Ariff (2017) defines it, includes cash, real estate, investments, and annual produce from societal labor. Wealth may also be referred to as the accumulation of all the savings and the investments by placing the savings transformed to investment in physical assets to create future wealth. He further deduces wealth to mean the total value of someone's assets less liabilities (Ariff & Mohamad, 2017). Wealth management (WM), a conventional financial service is similar to IWM that covers the financial planning, investment advice, portfolio management, accounting/tax services, and other financial services (Ting, 2017). Wealth Management which is a process of managing an individual or family's assets of which the value can increase or decrease over time entails a process from protecting and saving wealth, generating and accumulating wealth, and to distributing wealth during transition and retirement age (Basah & Tahir, 2019).

From the Islamic dimension, Wealth is not deduced to only mean material possession nor financial assets, but it take a unique perspective of including spiritual dimension (Ariff & Mohamad, 2017). Therefore, Islamic wealth has been explicitly and implicitly given significant attention to both material and spiritual possession in Quran. To appreciate the spiritual attention to wealth, Allah says in Quran (Suratul Sabah 34:37)

“It is not your wealth or children that bring you closer to Us. But those who believe and do good—it is they who will have a multiplied reward for what they did, and they will be secure in ‘elevated’ mansions.”

Islamic wealth, encompassing material and emotional dimensions, presents a holistic framework that makes Islamic wealth management a crucial area of study. This relevance stems from the objective to structure individual and societal wealth cycles within an ethically grounded economy (Basah & Tahir, 2019; Nasr, 2015). Al-Abbadi & Abdullah (2017) define Islamic Wealth Management (IWM) as a comprehensive process that includes wealth creation, accumulation, protection, distribution, and purification. Farooq (2014) references Ibn Sīnā's two-phase model of wealth management—wealth creation (income) and wealth utilization (expenditure)—both of which must adhere to Shariah principles. This ethical dimension of Islamic Wealth Management not only supports individual financial well-being but also emphasizes broader social welfare, reflecting a balance between personal and societal needs (Ismail & Antonio, 2012; Farooq, 2014).

Islam places strong emphasis on equitable wealth distribution, assigning responsibility to the wealthier sectors of society (Farooq, 2014). Islamic Wealth Management (IWM) encompasses financial planning and investment management aligned with Sharia principles, ensuring ethical compliance while offering competitive returns (Nurasyiah *et al.*, 2024). The process of IWM includes five stages: wealth creation, accumulation, protection/preservation, purification, and distribution (Basah & Tahir, 2019). Islamic wealth management has five key components: wealth creation, wealth accumulation, wealth purification, wealth protection, and wealth distribution. It primarily aims to provide a level of investment protection, generate and accumulate income and distribute wealth in accordance with the norms of Islamic law. In other words, it stipulates wealth creation through Shariah-compliant investment vehicles such as Islamic funds, sukuks and Islamic equities (Alshater *et al.*, 2021; Ariff & Mohamad, 2017).

Unlike conventional wealth management, IWM strictly avoids usury, uncertainty (*gharar*), gambling (*maysir*), and prohibited goods. With the rise of Islamic Banking and Finance, IWM has become an increasingly recognized approach, using both financial and non-financial instruments to manage wealth in accordance with Islamic values. IWM also supports the

sustainability of MSMEs, enhancing their stability and growth through Sharia-compliant investments (Nurasyiah *et al.*, 2024).

In Indonesia, scholars including Ismail (2014) explored Ibn-e-Sīnā's concepts of wealth management, particularly *tadbir al-manzil* (economics), aiming to develop a model that integrates material, spiritual, moral, social, and legal aspects. This holistic approach underscores the relevance of Ibn Sīnā's ideas in contemporary Islamic wealth management. The model's comprehensive nature makes it practical and valuable today. Further research is needed to assess the applicability of these insights in Uganda, specifically at IUIU-KC.

In Uganda, the inherent advantages of Islamic finance, particularly its interest-free nature, hold the potential to catalyze an inclusive economy. Yet, realizing these benefits hinges on dedicated research and concerted efforts by authorities to establish a robust legal and regulatory framework for the Islamic financial industry in the country. It is imperative to adapt the existing structure, aligning it with Islamic laws to enhance product offerings and service quality. However, it's crucial for all stakeholders to acknowledge the current limitations and collaboratively strive for advancements in this sector (Mutungi, 2018).

Moreover, employees in Uganda, encompassing not only those at the Islamic University Kampala Campus (IUIU KC), express a keen interest in wealth generation for securing savings and future investments. They prioritize their resources' security and seek wealth accumulation opportunities through prudent reinvestment (Burckart & Lydenberg, 2021). Some employees aspire to align their investments with Islamic principles, anticipating benefits for future use, whether for their descendants or during retirement (Mahdzan *et al.*, 2023).

Aligning wealth strategies with the Islamic wealth perspective offers substantial benefits, including sustainable wealth accumulation and equitable distribution, fostering both collective economic growth and improved quality of life. This approach contributes to the broader prosperity of individuals, households, communities, nations, and the global economy (Ariff & Mohamad, 2017; Basah & Tahir, 2019; Manj *et al.*, 2024). Nevertheless, a notable challenge arises with current, wealth management institutions like NSSF, and other organization-based saving schemes like Friends in Need Association, an IUIU - KC based saving scheme aimed to accumulate wealth of its members. There is insufficient evidence if any for implementation of IWM yet they lack alignment with Islamic principles that govern wealth management. This exclusivity becomes apparent when individuals seeking adherence to Islamic guidance are turned away. For example,

some saved institutions might accumulate interest, and fund managers may engage in non-halal activities like interest-based investments, gharar, or maysir so as to accumulate profit which may be later on be distributed at an agreed time.

Recognizing the need for inclusivity and the associated IWM benefits, a comprehensive study is warranted to investigate whether Islamic wealth management could address these issues (Shinkafi *et al.*, 2020). This study specifically aims to explore the viability of Islamic wealth management among staff at the Islamic University in Uganda, Kampala Campus, Kibuli Kampala.

1.1. General Objective

This study aimed to explore the viability of Islamic Wealth Management among Staff at the Islamic University in Uganda, Kampala Campus, Kibuli Kampala.

1.2. Specific Objectives of the Study

The following objectives guided the study,

- I. To establish how attitude influences the intention to adopt Islamic wealth management among the staff of IUIU-KC.
- II. To investigate how behavior beliefs, influence the intention to adopt Islamic wealth management among the staff of IUIU-KC.
- III. To examine how normative beliefs, influence the intention to adopt Islamic Wealth Management among the staff of IUIU-KC.

1.3. Research Questions

The study sought to answer the following research questions:

- I. Whether attitude influences the intention to adopt Islamic wealth management among the staff of IUIU-KC.
- II. Whether behavior beliefs influence the intention to adopt Islamic wealth management among the staff of IUIU-KC.
- III. Whether normative beliefs influence the intention to adopt Islamic Wealth Management among the staff of IUIU-KC.

1.4. Significance of the Study

The findings of this research have the potential to significantly impact wealth management practices in Uganda, promoting equitable distribution and cost efficiency. Islamic scholars may leverage these insights to advance financial literacy, while regulatory bodies like Uganda Retirement Benefits Regulatory Authority (URBRA) could consider aligning policies with principles of Islamic wealth creation. For fund managers, the study provides a framework for understanding Islamic wealth distribution, and it offers individuals engaged in conventional finance a perspective on the security of halal investments. The research targets a broad audience, including university students, Sharia scholars, entrepreneurs, fund managers, and policymakers, to foster inclusive, ethical financial practices.

2. Literature review

2.1. Theoretical Review

Numerous studies on service or product adoption have utilized theories like the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) (Nomi & Sabbir, 2020; Ajzen, 2020; Gazali, 2019), the Theory of Planned Behavior (Purbowisant *et al.*, 2021; Awn & Azam, 2020), and the Diffusion of Innovation Theory (Yahaya *et al.*, 2016). Most of these studies were conducted outside Uganda. This study emphasizes TRA, which Ajzen and Fishbein (1975) describe as elucidating the relationship between attitudes and behaviors, predicting behavior based on attitudes and intentions. In this context, the predicted behavior is the adoption of Islamic Wealth Management in Uganda.

TRA focuses on understanding voluntary behavior through underlying motivations (Doswell *et al.*, 2011), with intention as the principal predictor (Glanz *et al.*, 2015). Social norms also play a crucial role. TRA has been applied in various studies, including communication, consumer actions, and health decisions, and is effective when behaviors are objectively measured (Yousafzai & Shumaila, 2010). This study uses TRA to examine the adoption of Islamic Wealth Management in Uganda, specifically at IUIU-KC, to understand staff behavioral beliefs and the potential for this financial practice in the Ugandan context.

2.2. Conceptual Review

Where **Q1 – Attitude, Q2- Behavioral Beliefs, Q3 – Normative Beliefs**

Figure 1. Showing the Conceptual Framework of the study

Source: Modified by author.

From Figure 1, the study holds perceptions to imply attitudes, behavioral beliefs, and normative beliefs as independent variables that influence IWM which involves creation, accumulation, protection, distribution, and purification. In its finding, the study concludes that this relationship is further affected by intervening variables including educational initiatives, policy advocacy and continuous monitoring and evaluation.

2.3. Attitudes

According to the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), attitude is a critical factor influencing behavioral intention, reflecting individuals' feelings toward a specific behavior (Ajzen & Albarracín, 2007). Saygılı *et al.* (2022) found that "attitude," "social influence," and "self-efficacy" significantly affect intentions to use Islamic financial products. Attitudes depend on behavioral beliefs about anticipated outcomes and whether these are seen positively or negatively (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975; Savadori & Lauriola, 2021). Research consistently shows a strong link between perceived advantages and adoption (Echchabi & Aziz, 2012; Ho & Wu, 2011). This

underscores the importance of attitude in assessing Islamic Wealth Management's viability among IUIU-KC staff.

2.4. Behavioral Belief

Understanding the motivations behind IUIU-KC staff's engagement in Islamic Wealth Management (IWM) is essential for assessing its viability. Behavioral beliefs, as defined by Ajzen (2020), associate specific behaviors with expected outcomes, such as viewing Islamic financial products as pathways to both financial success and religious adherence (Ali *et al.*, 2021). The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) offers a framework for understanding how behavioral intentions drive actions, highlighting the roles of attitudes, social norms, and personal experience (Montano & Kasprzyk, 2015). Insights into these behavioral beliefs and the influence of social norms within the IUIU community are key to understanding intentions and engagement in IWM.

2.5. Normative Beliefs

Normative beliefs shape behavioral intentions by reflecting perceptions of how significant others—like family, friends, and peers—view certain behaviors (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). These beliefs influence whether individuals find behaviors socially acceptable, impacting their motivation to comply with social expectations (Andrews, 2020). For example, if one's social circle disapproves of a behavior, they are less likely to engage in it. Subjective norms, as part of normative beliefs, link the likelihood of performing a behavior to the approval or disapproval of referent groups, guiding behavior based on social acceptance (Montano & Kasprzyk, 2015).

2.6. Empirical Review

2.6.1. Attitude and Islamic Wealth Management

Islamic wealth creation is essential to Islamic wealth management, involving asset control and growth over time (Basah *et al.*, 2019; Akhmadjonov *et al.*, 2021). This process includes earning wealth throughout life stages and post-retirement, emphasizing fairness in banking practices guided by the Quran and Hadith. Attitudes play a crucial role, as stakeholders' beliefs and values shape their approach to wealth management. Islamic wealth creation promotes principled wealth generation, benefiting both the economy and society (Nurasyiah *et al.*, 2024).

Ismail (2012) explores Islamic wealth management from Ibn Sina's perspective, focusing on *Kasb* (earning) through trade and manufacturing. The study emphasizes that wealth should be earned through lawful, Sharia-compliant means, discouraging unethical practices. Akere (2016) explores Islamic wealth creation within the context of various economic models, underscoring its systematic and advantageous approach. Islamic law promotes the preservation, growth, and equitable distribution of resources through mechanisms such as Zakat and Sharia-compliant banks, which are essential for economic development (Alhammadi, 2024). Furthermore, Ramadani (2021) emphasizes the significance of the Islamic context as a catalyst for entrepreneurial activity, highlighting its crucial role in wealth creation and economic progress.

These studies collectively highlight the importance of ethical wealth creation and management in Islam, emphasizing fairness, lawful earning, and societal benefit. This literature supports the viability of Islamic wealth management among IUIU staff by aligning financial practices with Islamic principles.

2.6.2. Behavior Beliefs and Islamic Wealth Management

Ab Aziza *et al.* (2014) indicate that many Muslims neglect wealth distribution planning, leading to potential conflicts. Islamic doctrine emphasizes wealth distribution to foster societal wealth accumulation and has established principles for the *maslahah* (welfare) of humanity. Muslims are encouraged to align their needs and aspirations with Islamic teachings, requiring a shift in behavior. Mechanisms like Zakat (obligatory almsgiving) and Sharia-compliant banking promote resource preservation, growth, and equitable distribution. Islam's comprehensive approach to human development stresses achieving *Maqasid al-Shariah* (objectives of Islamic law), which include justice, equality, and social welfare. Aligning behaviors with these objectives is essential in public policy to ensure actions benefit societal well-being and economic development (Zailani *et al.*, 2022; Purbowisanti *et al.*, 2021).

Ismail (2012) argues that wealth acquired through fair means should be divided equally: half for charity and good deeds, and half for savings and retirement. This practice is grounded in the Islamic belief in the oneness of Allah (*al-Tawāḍ*), which permits individuals to use their wealth for personal needs while directing surplus funds towards charitable purposes or reinvestment to seek Allah's pleasure. Islamic teachings emphasize acquiring wealth through *halal* (permissible) means and advocate for a religiously guided approach to wealth distribution among households,

corporations, and governments. Additionally, these teachings stress the importance of saving for future contingencies, ensuring both individual and collective financial stability and adherence to Islamic principles (Calder, 2020).

According to Waqqas *et al.* (2016), Islamic wealth distribution, grounded in divine teachings, emphasizes ethical values like generosity and charity. It involves two aspects: primary, which rewards production contributors (land, labor, capital, entrepreneurs) with rent, wages, interest, and profit; and secondary, which addresses the needs of non-producers, including orphans, widows, and the poor, through wealth redistribution.

El Gamal (2008) describes the Islamic finance industry (IFI) as primarily prohibition-driven, focusing on avoiding practices like interest and gambling. Although IFI has achieved positive results compared to conventional finance, it may not fully align with Islamic principles or broader socio-economic goals. Kloppenburg (2007) notes that early supporters of IFI might have breached the Quranic principle against wealth concentration by engaging in usury, leading to a potentially skewed wealth distribution and societal stagnation.

Stiglitz (2012) highlights that true economic growth and wealth accumulation should be accompanied by a broader reduction in poverty and an improved standard of living for the entire population. This approach not only strengthens the middle class but also enhances asset ownership. From an Islamic perspective, wealth management should go beyond mere accumulation to also focus on increasing asset and capital ownership, promoting a more inclusive and equitable society.

2.6.3. Normative Beliefs and Islamic Wealth Management

Normative beliefs, or perceived social pressures, significantly influence behavioral intentions in Islamic wealth management (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). These beliefs determine whether individuals perceive certain behaviors as socially acceptable, which impacts their financial decisions (Wang & Pan, 2024). For example, if IUIU staff believe their peers support Islamic wealth management, they are more likely to engage in it.

The importance of normative beliefs is highlighted by the Islamic requirements for wealth purification through Zakah (charity) and Sadaqah (donations) (Lahsasna, 2017). Studies indicate that social norms and community expectations play a crucial role in promoting Islamic wealth

management practices, emphasizing fairness, lawful earning, and societal benefit (Ahcene, 2017; Hassan, 2024). Additionally, financial literacy and education enhance these practices, ensuring that both individuals and corporations comply with Islamic principles (Saifurrahman & Kassim, 2021).

2.7. Research Gap

Given the impact of key events in the global economy including but not limited to COVID-19 pandemic, the Russian-Ukraine war, the Israel – Palestine war, the homosexuality campaign among others, business prospects have been giving a new approach across the spectrum of strategic managers. A key focus among higher education institutions, IUIU inclusive becomes more relevant given that they are the hub for the knowledge and research. Though prevailing literature has greatly highlighted the essence of Islamic wealth Management, we need to further contribute literature in the Uganda's local perspective, more specifically at IUIU -KC. This will enable future researchers and policy stakeholders to have informed decisions while implementing aspects relating to wealth management.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design and Approach

The study adopted a qualitative-exploratory approach, effective for investigating perspectives on a given phenomenon (Corte, 2019). Allan (2020) highlights that this approach captures respondents' attitudes, opinions, and behaviours, hence finding it suitable for in-depth exploration of how viability of IWM to staff social economic transformation making it relevant for studying the viability of Islamic wealth management among IUIU-KC staff.

3.2. Study Participants

The Islamic University in Uganda, Kampala Campus (IUIU-KC), has 162 full-time academic staff across seven faculties, including Arts and Social Sciences, Management Studies, Law, and Islamic Studies and Arabic Language. This study focused specifically on the Faculty of Management Studies due to its staff's extensive academic experience in Islamic Wealth Management. Out of the 22 academic staff in this faculty, purposive sampling was used to select 12 staff members known for their deep familiarity with Islamic Wealth Management. Purposive sampling targets individuals strategically positioned to provide relevant insights (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003; Malhotra, 2007). Following Baker and Edwards (2012), who recommend 12 to 101 participants for qualitative studies, this sample size aimed for representativeness and precision, ensuring that findings accurately reflect reality (Amin, 2005; Singh & Masuku, 2014; Uma Sekaran, 2003).

3.3. Data Collection Instruments

Data collection instruments reflect techniques that enable the researcher to gather the required data to answer the key research question. To this end, data was collected through 1 set of an interview guide as follows.

3.4. Interview Guide

An interview is a dialogue between interviewer and interviewee to gather data (Mason, 2002). The researcher used a structured interview guide with IUIU-KC staff due to its flexibility and adaptability (Neuman, 2011). Interviews encouraged participants to express their thoughts and feelings (Berg, 2007) and provided in-depth information on the topic (McNamara, 1999). This method allowed the researcher to clarify answers and gather insights on adopting Islamic wealth management in Uganda.

3.5. Data Quality Control

Brock-Utne (1996) emphasizes that validity and reliability are essential in qualitative research, similar to quantitative research. To ensure these, a pilot study was conducted to test the data collection tools (Silverman, 2010). Reliability—interpreted as dependability and consistency—was addressed by pre-testing questions with selected individuals from IUIU-KC's Bursary

department, where many have expertise in finance. Kvale and Brinkmann (2009) propose criteria such as trustworthiness, credibility, dependability, and confirmability to assess research quality. In this study, credibility was used to confirm the believability of findings, transferability assessed the data's applicability to other contexts, and confirmability examined how much the investigator's values influenced the research.

3.6. Data Analysis

3.6.1. Qualitative Data Analysis

Qualitative data from interviews was transcribed verbatim and verified by re-reading. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data, and both thematic and content analysis techniques were employed to highlight individual respondents' views (Mason, 2002). The data was synthesized and classified to aid in preliminary interpretation, summary, and integration into the study's key variables, forming the basis for final conclusions and recommendations.

3.7. Ethical Considerations

It is important to recall that ethics in research are a primary consideration rather than an afterthought (Resnik, 2015). Any one undertaking research must put the ethical issues at the forefront of whatever they do. The researcher shall seek to uphold the key ethical values prudent to scientific research as follows:

Informed Consent: the researcher ensured that respondents are made aware of the purpose of the study as well as responding to the items with full knowledge and conviction. This was included in the first section of the Interview Guide. As for interview respondents, the explanation about the study purpose was made at the time of fixing appointments.

Originality: to achieve this, the researcher sought to realise originality through observing proper citation rules and checking the work for plagiarism using the Turnitin software.

Confidentiality: here the researcher ensured that the names of respondents are not revealed directly and were not asked to write their names anywhere on the Interview Guide.

Anonymity: the researcher ensured that the findings were not traceable to the respondents. To afford this, respondents to the interview guide were coded and the codes were used for reference

4. Results and Discussion

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the prospects of adopting Islamic Wealth Management at IUIU-KC. The findings were organized into three themes:

1. **Willingness to Adopt Islamic Wealth Management:** This theme explored staff opinions, beliefs, and perceived benefits.
2. **Fulfilling Sharia Requirements:** This theme examined how to meet Sharia requirements and ways to encourage others to practice Islamic Wealth Management.
3. **Perceptions and Support:** This theme investigated perceptions of Islamic Wealth Management and identified supporters.

The findings addressed the study's guiding question on the prospects of adopting Islamic Wealth Management among IUIU-KC staff. Data was collected through interviews, with participants anonymized as A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, and I.

4.1. Response Rate

The Study targeted 12 respondents and the researcher accessed 9 making it 70%. This was a good sample for research. The researcher felt that the response rate was appropriate since Gordon (2002) contends that a response rate of 70%–80% is ideal for any study.

4.2. Demographic Data Analysis

This study collected demographic information to examine how variables like age, gender, and education might influence the results. This section presents a descriptive analysis of these demographic variables.

4.3. Gender of Respondents

The study sought to establish the gender representation in the study sample in order to ascertain whether there was gender disparity in data collection and to balance the views of both genders based on the study objectives. The study attracted 5 males and 4 females.

4.4. Level of Education

This study aimed to ascertain the educational qualifications of the respondents, and the distribution by level of education is outlined. Among the 9 respondents, it was found that 1 held a Ph.D., 6 possessed master's degrees, and 2 held bachelor's degrees. The diverse educational backgrounds of the respondents encompass all levels within the university, ensuring a comprehensive representation of the educational spectrum.

4.5. Age of Respondents

The study assessed the age distribution of respondents: 1 was aged 25-30, 4 were 31-45, 3 were 46-50, and 1 was 51-60. Most respondents were mature, reflecting their ability to make informed decisions due to their experience, aligning with Aloka and Bojuwoye (2013), who noted that older individuals tend to make more considered decisions.

Objective One: To Establish how Attitude will Influence the Intention to Adopt Islamic Wealth Management among the Staff of IUIU-KC.

This objective explored various opinions and beliefs about the Willingness of the staff of IUIU-KC to adopt Islamic Wealth Management as theme one. It also examined the benefits/values of Islamic wealth management as theme two. Data from all the respondents on these themes is summarized in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively.

Theme one: WILLINGNESS OF THE STAFF OF IUIU-KC TO ADOPT ISLAMIC WEALTH MANAGEMENT

This study obtained qualitative responses on item that, “In your view would you take up Islamic wealth management and why? Respondents pointed out the following views as seen in Table 4.

Table 1 shows that all respondents supported Islamic wealth management. This is so because most of them saw it as the best decision to take in order to practice their religion very well.

Respondent D said the following about taking up Islamic wealth management

“Yes I would take it because it’s the best way to earn money and spend it according to the Quran and Hadith”

Table 1. Willingness to Adopt Islamic Wealth Management

S/N	Respondent	Response
1.	A	yes, Feel okay with it
2.	B	Yes, it is good system
3.	C	Yes, feel at peace practicing it
4.	D	Yes, okay with it
5.	E	Yes, it is the best idea
6.	F	Yes, it is the best way
7.	G	Yes, not a bad idea
8.	H	Yes, Best option
9.	I	Yes, Best decision

Source: Primary Data

The study's findings align with Ismail (2012), who emphasizes earning through permissible means rather than unethical methods. Respondents prefer earning and spending in line with Qur'anic and Hadith principles. Basah *et al.* (2019) support this by noting that Islamic wealth creation is crucial to Islamic wealth management, involving strategic asset management to enhance family wealth according to Islamic principles.

Theme Two: Benefits/Values of Islamic Wealth Management

This study obtained qualitative responses on item that, “What are the benefits/values of Islamic wealth management?” The findings of this broad theme are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2 reveals that respondents highlighted several benefits of Islamic Wealth Management, notably the importance of earning halal income and avoiding displeasing Allah. This aligns with Ismail (2012), who stresses obtaining livelihood through ethical means according to Qur'anic and Hadith principles. Respondents also emphasized equitable wealth distribution, a viewpoint supported by Akere (2016), which notes that Islamic wealth creation integrates with other economic models and ensures fair resource distribution through mechanisms like Zakat,

inheritance, and natural resources. Financial institutions, including Sharia-compliant banks, play a crucial role in this process.

Table 2. Benefits of Islamic Wealth Management

S.N	Respondent	Response
1.	A	Equality Keeps one from unlawful/ haram One is mindful of spending
2.	B	Protected by teachings of Islam Does not entertain interest No grabbing other people’s wealth
3.	C	Gain Allah’s blessings in its practice Protect one from harmful investments
4.	D	Develops society Improves social wellbeing of people
5.	E	Prohibits exploitation of people
6.	F	Earn pure wealth Gain Allah’s blessings
7.	G	No haram earnings
8.	H	Distributes wealth equitable
9.	I	There is equity Bring peace in communities

Source: Primary Data

This explains why respondents were fully in support of Islamic wealth management.

Respondent B said ; *“With Islamic Wealth Management it is much protected by the teachings of Islam so you do not need to grab other people’s wealth and take it to be yours.....It does not entertain riba and helps to guide on how to manage our wealth.....”*

The respondent’s remarks are supported Al-Qur’ān:(51:56-58) in which Allah says

” ...And I did not create the jinn and mankind except to worship Me. I do not want

from them any provision, nor do I want them to feed me. Indeed, it is Allah who is the [continual] Provider, the firm possessor of strength”.

The respondents' views align with El Gamal (2008), who notes that Islamic finance is grounded in prohibitions, such as ribā, gharar, and maysir. The respondents' concerns about avoiding ribā reflect a strong commitment to adhering to these Islamic principles and avoiding actions that could displease Allah.

Objective Two: To investigate how Behavior Beliefs will Influence the Intention to Adopt Islamic Wealth Management among the Staff of IUIU-KC.

This objective examined fulfilling the Sharia Requirements for Islamic Wealth Management as theme three and theme four explored avenues or ways of Encouraging Others to Practice Islamic Wealth Management. The findings of this broad theme is summarized in Table 3 and Table 4 respectively.

Theme Three: Requirements for Fulfilling Sharia for Islamic Wealth Management

This study obtained qualitative responses on item that, “how would you fulfill the Sharia Requirements for Islamic Wealth Management?”. The findings of this theme are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3 reveals that respondents prioritized charity, viewing it as both a compassionate act and a means of purifying their wealth. This aligns with Ismail (2012), who notes that ethical wealth accumulation should include Sadaqah and Zakat, with the remainder saved for future needs. Respondents, guided by the belief in al-Tawīd, see surplus wealth as suitable for charity or reinvestment, reflecting a Sharia-compliant approach to wealth management.

It's also worthy to note that a given proportion of respondents like A were against earning interest (Ribah). This is so because it's a great sin in front of Allah. Respondents reported that taking ribah puts someone in a fight with Allah. Respondent A remarked

“You do not take up interest because it is not allowed in sharia and do not

involve in unlawful business.”

El Gamal (2008) highlights that the Islamic finance industry is fundamentally prohibition-driven, adhering strictly to bans on ribā, gharar, maysir, and other forbidden transactions. This explains why most respondents avoid money involving interest.

Table 3. Fulfilling the Sharia Requirements for Islamic Wealth Management

S/N	RESPONDENTS	RESPONSE
1.	A	Not taking and giving interest Invest in lawful ventures
2.	B	Acquire halal wealth Not taking interest
3.	C	Researching about the lawful ventures Spending within ones ‘means
4.	D	Not charging interest Sharing benefits and losses on investments
5.	E	Avoiding exploitation of people Not involving in unlawful business
6.	F	Follow teachings of Quran Gain Allah’s blessings
7.	G	Giving charity Spending within one’ means
8.	H	Distributes wealth equitable Learn the do’s and don’ts of Quran
9.	I	Give charity Seek guidance from professionals

Source: Primary Data

Theme four: Encouraging others to practice Islamic Wealth Management

This theme explored on the ways of Encouraging Others to Practice Islamic Wealth Management. The findings of this theme are summarized in Table 4.

From the findings in Table 4, Respondent A, B, C, D, F and I all asserted that there was need to explain to the people the benefits of Islamic Wealth Management. This is because majority of the people have been taken up by the conventional wealth management and the Dunia which will not favor mankind in the hereafter. Indeed, the findings of the respondents are

supported by Al Quran (18: 1-3) where Allah says

“[All] praise is [due] to Allah, who has sent down upon His Servant the Book and has not made therein any deviance. [He has made it] straight, to warn of severe punishment from Him and to give good tidings to the believers who do righteous deeds that they will have a good reward. In which they will remain forever”

The Quran, revealed by Allah to guide humanity, includes principles on Islamic Wealth Management and warns of consequences for not following its teachings.

Respondent I remarked

“I would encourage them by showing them the importance of engaging in Islamic wealth management , then I would also try to call people to practice the Islamic religion because it is the one which teaches Islamic wealth management and I would also try to practice it what I preach so as others can learn from me.”

Table 4. Encourage Others to Practice Islamic Wealth Management

S/N	Respondent	Response
1.	A	Explain the benefits of IWM Avoid interest on income
2.	B	By sensitizing people on IWM
3.	C	Showing the benefits of IWM Involving them in partnership business
4.	D	Explaining the benefits of IWM
5.	E	By being exemplary to them
6.	F	By sensitizing people
7.	G	By practicing it to be exemplary
8.	H	Distributing wealth equitable
9.	I	Explaining the benefits of IWM Practicing IWM Preaching Islam

Source: Primary Data

Nadvi (2005) highlights that Prophet Muhammad's teachings on economic and political matters were designed to guide humanity toward eternal success, balancing worldly affairs with spiritual goals. This underscores the significance of Islamic wealth management, as emphasized by the Prophet and his successors.

Objective Three: To Examine how Normative Beliefs will Influence the Intention to Adopt Islamic Wealth Management among the Staff of IUIU-KC.

Objective three delved into the Perception of People Towards Islamic Wealth Management as the five and the sixth theme examined Who Supports Islamic wealth Management. Descriptive findings of this theme are summarized in Table 4:5 and Table 4:6 respectively

Theme Five: Perception of the People in your Area (home and work) about Islamic Wealth Management.

This theme explored on: “what is the perception of the people in your area (home and work) about Islamic wealth management?” The findings of this theme are summarized in table 4:5.

Table 5 shows that most respondents view Islamic Wealth Management (IWM) positively and support its adoption. They particularly value its role in equitable wealth distribution and income purification. This aligns with Ahcene (2017), who emphasized wealth purification through charity, and Swadjaja *et al.* (2019), who noted that IWM focuses on maximizing returns while adhering to Islamic principles. Respondent C supports IWM for its prohibition of ribā, a serious sin in Islam, aligning with El Gamal's (2008) observation that the Islamic finance industry strictly adheres to prohibitions.

Respondent A, D and H perceived IWM as a good idea because it protects the teaching of Islam the Quran and Hadiths of the Prophet (SAW) this is supported by by Al Quran (18: 1-3) where Allah says

“ [All] praise is [due] to Allah, who has sent down upon His Servant the Book and has not made therein any deviance. [He has made it] straight, to warn of severe punishment from Him and to give good tidings to the believers who do righteous deeds that they will have a good reward. In which they will remain forever”

Table 5. Perception of People towards Islamic Wealth Management

S/N	Respondent	Response		Reason
		Good	Bad	
1.	A	✓		They are Muslims and believe in Islamic teachings
2.	B		✓	They are not Muslims and think that it is attached to Islam as a religion
3.	C	✓		it does not involve taking of interest (riba)
4.	D	✓		It brings about peace, security and stability in the economy
5.	E	✓		It is advocates for equitable distribution of wealth
6.	F	✓		It is aims at development of the society
7.	G		✓	It improves the social wellbeing of the poor
8.	H	✓		It protects ones' wealth from destruction
9.	I	✓		It increases the purchasing power of people

Source: Primary Data

The Quran guides us on all aspects of life, including Islamic Wealth Management, and warns of consequences for not following its teachings. Most respondents adhere to these teachings. However, some express negative views on Islamic Wealth Management, citing concerns about deepening inequality or perceiving it as an attempt to Islamize the economy.

Respondent B remarked

“ what I see and think about this is that people do not want to take it because they think, it will end up making every one a Muslim, because they believe that one you practice a teaching of a religion, you end up believing in it and so they practice the conventional way of wealth management, but I guess that with time if they are provided with more information about Islamic wealth management, they will embrace it.”

This aligns with Fishbein and Ajzen's (1975) Theory of Reasoned Action which suggests that beliefs shape perceptions and intentions regarding behavior. According to this theory, individuals will adopt Islamic Wealth Management based on their beliefs and norms.

Theme six: “Who Support of Islamic Wealth Management in Uganda. The findings in this sub theme are summarized in Table 6 as seen below.

This theme explored on: “Who do you think is in support of Islamic wealth management in Uganda?” The findings of this theme are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6. Who Supports Islamic wealth Management

S/N	RESPONDENTS	RESPONSE
1.	A	Muslim bodies Mosque leaders (Religious leaders)
2.	B	Muslims
3.	C	The government of Uganda Islamic religious leaders
4.	D	Muslims
5.	E	Islamic institutions like IUIU-KC and UMSC
6.	F	Muslims
7.	G	The government of Uganda Islamic institutions like zakat and waqf
8.	H	Islamic institutions Religious leaders
9.	I	Muslims Small business owners

Source: Primary Data

According to Table 6, most respondents believe that Muslims and Muslim leaders should support Islamic Wealth Management (IWM). This view aligns with the Ng, A. (2019), which highlights that Waqf assets, like mosques and Islamic schools, play a key role in wealth redistribution and social development. These leaders, well-versed in Sharia, inspire confidence in managing IWM effectively.

Respondent I remarked

“The main people that we have here are the Muslims, the Muslim fraternity, they are the ones that are opting/ that are pushing for /who support Islamic Wealth Management. The other ones are the small business owners who normally make loses especially during times when they get loans from banks and end up losing their goods due to interest charged that keeps on multiplying , so they would want to have where they can also benefit because they are small

earners, they would like to get small loans which are riba/interest free to boost their capital, so as to expand their businesses.”

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

5.1. Conclusion

The conclusions that have been derived in this study are based on the findings in respect to the specific objectives of the study and their implications in the view of the researcher and are presented as follows:

Objective One: To Establish how Attitude will Influence the Intention to Adopt Islamic Wealth Management among the Staff of IUIU-KC.

This study explored how attitudes shape the intention to adopt Islamic wealth management among IUIU-KC staff, focusing on their perceptions and values. Two guiding questions framed this inquiry: "Would you take up Islamic wealth management and how do you feel about it?" and "What are the benefits/values of Islamic wealth management?" Responses were analyzed thematically, and findings (as shown in Tables 4.1 and 4.2) reflected positive views toward Islamic wealth management. Participants expressed that adopting Islamic wealth management would allow for wealth purification, the attainment of Allah's blessings, and assurance of halal earnings. These findings are consistent with Basah *et al.* (2019), who emphasize that positive attitudes play a critical role in motivating the adoption of Islamic wealth management. By fostering favorable perceptions, IUIU-KC staff recognize the spiritual and ethical dimensions of Islamic wealth practices, which reinforce their willingness to embrace this model as an alternative to conventional approaches.

Objective Two: To Investigate how Behavior Beliefs will Influence the Intention to Adopt Islamic Wealth Management among the Staff of IUIU-KC.

This study examined how behavioral beliefs shape the intention to adopt Islamic wealth management among IUIU-KC staff, specifically through their perceived ability to fulfill Sharia requirements and to promote Islamic wealth management practices in Uganda. Two key questions guided this investigation: "How would you fulfill the Sharia requirements for Islamic wealth

management in Uganda?" and "How would you encourage others to practice Islamic wealth management?" Thematic analysis, detailed in Tables 4.3 and 4.4, revealed predominantly positive themes, indicating strong, supportive beliefs in meeting these requirements and encouraging the adoption of Islamic wealth management.

Respondents demonstrated a clear commitment to fulfilling Sharia principles, viewing compliance as both achievable and beneficial for ethical financial practices. This sense of responsibility was coupled with a proactive desire to advocate for Islamic wealth management by emphasizing its advantages, such as ethical investment and wealth purification, to their peers. Such positive behavioral beliefs align with a readiness to integrate Islamic principles into wealth management, indicating that IUIU-KC staff members are likely to support and adopt Islamic wealth management due to their favorable views on its Sharia-based requirements and their willingness to promote its values.

The study concludes that these supportive behavioral beliefs play a crucial role in fostering a strong intention to adopt Islamic wealth management among the staff. By acknowledging the importance of fulfilling Sharia obligations and actively promoting Islamic wealth management, staff members reinforce their own intentions while potentially influencing a broader cultural shift within their institution toward adopting Islamic financial practices.

Objective Three: To Examine how Normative Beliefs will Influence the Intention to Adopt Islamic Wealth Management among the Staff of IUIU-KC.

This study examined how normative beliefs affect the intention to adopt Islamic wealth management among IUIU-KC staff. Using two qualitative questions—"What is the perception of people in your area about Islamic Wealth Management?" and "Who supports Islamic wealth management in Uganda?"—the thematic analysis (Tables 4.5 and 4.6) revealed positive themes. Respondents' normative beliefs were supportive, enhancing the intention to adopt Islamic wealth management. Thus, the study concludes that normative beliefs positively influence the adoption of Islamic wealth management among IUIU-KC staff.

5.2. Recommendations

This study investigated the on the influence of attitude, behavior beliefs and normative beliefs on the intention to adopt Islamic wealth management among the staff of IUIU-KC. Based on the key

findings of this study the following recommendations were suggested in respect to the objectives of this study:

Objective One: To Establish how Attitude Influences the Intention to Adopt Islamic Wealth Management among the Staff of IUIU-KC.

The findings of this study should be shared with IUIU-KC management, other educational institutions, financial institutions, government regulators, development partners, and civil society organizations. These stakeholders can use the insights to enhance strategies for promoting financial security, inclusivity, and equitable income distribution—key aspects of Islamic Wealth Management. The positive attitudes toward Islamic wealth management suggest that well-designed programs, if implemented broadly, can achieve sustainable wealth distribution and management across the population.

Objective Two and Objective Three: To Investigate how Behavior and Normative Beliefs will Influence the Intention to Adopt Islamic Wealth Management among the Staff of IUIU-KC.

Stakeholders, particularly Islamic institutions, recognizing the benefits associated with Islamic wealth management, should take deliberate steps to instil positive norms among their staff and the broader community. This can be achieved through:

Educational Initiatives: Implement educational programs to provide comprehensive knowledge about Islamic wealth management. This includes workshops, seminars, and training sessions aimed at enhancing understanding and awareness among staff and community members. This may also address the negative perception regarding that such Islamic finance initiatives are only a reserve of Muslims yet they are universal in nature (Yahaya *et al*, 2016).

Policy Advocacy: Advocate for policies that support the integration of Islamic wealth management principles. Engage with relevant authorities to ensure the creation of an enabling environment for the adoption of Islamic financial practices.

Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation: Implement ongoing monitoring and evaluation mechanisms, including feedback sessions, seminars, and focused group discussions. These activities serve as valuable tools to assess attitudes, perceptions, and behaviors over time, allowing stakeholders to track progress and ensure the sustained viability of Islamic wealth management in Uganda.

The study suggests that implementing these recommendations can contribute to fostering a supportive environment and encouraging the adoption of Islamic wealth management practices among the staff of IUIU-KC.

5.3. Implications of the study

The findings imply that fostering these positive perceptions can enhance IWM integration within educational and financial institutions. By understanding these key drivers, policymakers, educators, and financial institutions can develop targeted strategies to promote IWM adoption. This approach not only aids stakeholder engagement and curriculum refinement in higher education institutions (HEIs) but also supports informed policy-making, advancing the broader acceptance and integration of IWM in Uganda and similar contexts.

5.4. Recommendations for Further Research

No doubt, the global quest for alternative modes of wealth management, Islamic wealth management inclusive, researching wealth management is crucial for advancing the UN Sustainable Development Goals. Future studies should explore the viability of Islamic wealth management in various sectors beyond education in Africa and employ diverse research methods for a broader perspective.

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